
EUROSCITIZEN COST ACTION - VIRTUAL NETWORKING SUPPORT GRANT 2021

Guidelines for **Moderators** of Virtual COST Meetings

Date Created: 24th September 2021

This article/publication is based upon work from COST Action < CA17127 Building on scientific literacy in Evolution towards scientifically responsible Europeans >, supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology).
www.euroscitizen.eu

Authors:

Joelyn de Lima, Lilian Smith

Please note – meetings and the budget for the moderation support (Local Organiser Support) need to be approved by the MC and COST before being planned

Zoom Account Login Details	1
At least 20 days before the event	1
At least 14 days before the event	1
At least 1-2 days before the event	2
30 minutes before the event	3
During the event	3
After the event	4
Within 10 days of the event	4

Zoom Account Login Details

Will be provided by the respective WG leader as and when needed

At least 20 days before the event

- Meeting between Meeting Organiser and Moderator
- Agreement* on the following:
 - Dates and times for the moderation services
 - Hourly rate
 - Date and time for the briefing meeting

*for a template agreement please see Annex A

At least 14 days before the event

- Make sure you have received the event details from the Meeting Organiser (title, date(s), time(s) and participants list)
- Based on the event requirements, decide which Zoom format would work best: meetings or webinars.
- Schedule the event in Zoom and share the Zoom link with the Meeting Organiser and the Grant Holder (GH) Manager
- While setting up the zoom event please ensure that the following options are enabled (see screenshot):
 - Waiting Room
 - Mute participants upon entry
 - Automatic recording

Security

Passcode

Only users who have the invite link or passcode can join the meeting

Waiting Room

Only users admitted by the host can join the meeting

Require authentication to join

Video

Host on off

Participant on off

Audio

Telephone Computer Audio Both

Dial from United States [Edit](#)

Meeting Options

Allow participants to join anytime

Mute participants upon entry

Breakout Room pre-assign

Automatically record meeting On the local computer In the cloud

- For additional suggestions about setting up Zoom events, including avoiding/dealing with Zoombombing/trolls please refer to the document 'Instructions to set up Zoom events'.

At least 1-2 days before the event

- Meet with the Meeting Organiser to get briefed on the exact meeting schedule
- Make sure you understand the timeline and technical requirements of the meeting (breakout rooms, polls etc.)
- Wherever possible, set up breakout rooms and polls in advance
- If there are any documents/links that are going to be shared during the meeting, make sure that you have access to them.

30 minutes before the event

- Log in to the meeting early
- Rename yourself as follows: Moderator_First Name_Last Name
- Share your screen displaying the Zoom etiquette (Annex B)
- Assign co-host rights to the Meeting Organiser(s) and to the presenters
- Request them to rename themselves with their role or affiliation preceding their names.
- Test the audio/visual and screen sharing by the presenters. Troubleshoot if necessary.
- Allow participants in the waiting room to join the meeting (it is easier to keep an overview if you let them in one by one, rather than all at the same time). Make sure you are screening for potential disruptions. It is possible for you to send a chat message to the participants in the waiting room in case required.
- Welcome all newcomers, draw their attention to the Zoom etiquette and ask them to rename themselves as discussed : e.g. Country_First Name_Last Name or Institution_First Name_Last name
- Offer assistance on how to rename oneself and feedback options

During the event

- Start the recording (if it does not start automatically)
- Screen waiting room and let latecomers join
- Welcome latecomers via chat (individual chat if possible) and draw their attention to the Zoom etiquette and ask them to re-name themselves.
- Launch/Create and close break-out rooms/polls/surveys as discussed with the Meeting Organisers
- Share links/documents in the chat as and when required by the organisers.
- Monitor the chat. Please make sure that the discussions are civil and appropriate. Warn participants if they do not follow the norms.

- Monitor the participant list to call on people who have raised their hands. If people do not lower their hands after speaking, lower it for them.
- In case of disruptions to the meeting, please mute the disrupter, or move them to the waiting room, or eject them from the meeting.

After the event

- Stop the recording.
- If the Meeting Organisers want to debrief in the same zoom room, transfer the participants who have not yet disconnected to the waiting room.
- Make sure you save the chat.
- Download the necessary records.*

* for instructions check Annex C and D – **please pay special attention to the formatting requirements of the meeting registration and poll reports!**

Within 10 days of the event

- Submit the link to the cloud recording, meeting registration and poll reports to the Meeting Organiser and the GH Manager*
- If you had saved the recording to your local computer (this is not advisable) please upload it to the agreed upon cloud space as soon as possible and delete the recording from your computer.
- Submit your invoice to the Meeting Organiser and the GH Manager

* for instructions check Annex C and D – **please pay special attention to the formatting requirements of the meeting registration and poll reports!**

Annex A

EUROSCITIZEN COST ACTION

Agreement

Between (*insert name of Meeting Organiser*), hereafter called Meeting Organiser

And (*insert name of Moderator / Moderator Institution*); hereafter called Moderator

The Moderator agrees to moderate a virtual/hybrid event for the COST Action CA17127 at the following conditions:

Meeting title:

Meeting date(s) & time(s):

Estimated number of hours:

Hourly rate in Euros:

The briefing meeting will take place on (at least one full day before the actual meeting):

In order to be reimbursed, the Moderator agrees to comply with all requirements as set forth in the “EuroScitizen – Guidelines for Moderators of Virtual COST Meetings” and confirms that they can legally issue an invoice.

Place, Date

Meeting Organiser

Place, Date

Moderator

Annex B

Zoom etiquette

1. Please note you are muted by default. Please remember to unmute yourself only when speaking
2. Please re-name yourself as follows: Country_First Name_Last Name or Institution_First Name_Last name
3. Please ask your questions in the chat or raise your hand (raise hand function at the bottom of the participants list)
4. Please do not take any screenshots/photos of other participants' names or video.
5. Please note that this meeting is being recorded.

Annex C

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Zoom recordings and reports – detailed instructions

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These screenshots have been taken from the EuroScitizen Zoom account. Depending on the zoom account you are using, the pathway to locate the reports might be different.

Recording files

The screenshot shows the Zoom Cloud Recordings interface. On the left is a navigation menu with 'Recordings' highlighted. The main area is titled 'Cloud Recordings' and includes filters for date (From: mm/dd/yyyy, To: 09/24/2021) and status (All Status). There are search fields for ID, meeting number, and audio transcript, along with 'Search' and 'Export' buttons. Below are 'Delete Selected' and 'Delete All' buttons. A table lists recordings with columns for Topic, ID, Start Time, and File Size. Two recordings are visible: 'EuroScitizen SSI transversal meeting' (ID: 822 5663 3745, Start Time: May 25, 2021 02:23 PM, File Size: 3 Files (1.09 GB)) and 'Teste' (ID: 899 0908 1272, Start Time: May 25, 2021 11:20 AM, File Size: 3 Files (31 MB)). Each row has 'Share...' and 'More' buttons.

Generating reports

The screenshot shows the Zoom Usage Reports interface. The left navigation menu has 'Account Management' expanded, with 'Account Settings' highlighted. The main area is titled 'Usage Reports' and 'User Activity Reports'. A list of report types is shown with descriptions:

- Daily: Show daily number of new users, meetings, participants and meeting minutes in a month.
- Active Hosts: View meetings, participants and meeting minutes within a specified time range.
- Inactive Hosts: Show the users who are not active during a period.
- Upcoming Events: View upcoming meetings and webinars.
- Meeting: View registration reports and poll reports for meetings.
- Cloud Recording: View detailed information about cloud storage usage by host.
- Remote Support: View in-meeting support sessions during a certain period.

Participants

Reports - Usage Reports - Active Hosts Document

From: 09/23/2021 To: 09/24/2021 Search

Maximum report duration: 1 Month
 Reports show information for meetings that ended at least 15 minutes ago.

By Meetings By Users Report Queue

[Export as CSV File](#) [Generate details report](#) [Toggle columns](#)

Topic	Meeting ID	User Name	User Email	Department	Group	Has Zoom Rooms?	Creation Time	Start Time	End Time	Duration (Minutes)	Participants	Source
WG3 group meeting	891 9540 2073	EuroScitizen COST Action	euroscitizen@gmail.com			No	07/13/2021 12:48:44 AM	09/23/2021 10:04:29 PM	09/23/2021 10:11:21 PM	7	4	Zoom

Meeting Participants

Export with meeting data Report to Zoom Export

Name (Original Name)	User Email	Join Time	Leave Time	Duration (Minutes)	Guest
Tanja Adnadević		09/20/2021 11:59:47 AM	09/20/2021 12:52:53 PM	54	Yes
Johan (HGUT)		09/20/2021 12:01:04 PM	09/20/2021 12:20:16 PM	20	Yes

Registration, poll, survey reports

Reports - Usage Reports - Meeting Document

Meeting Report Report Queue

Report Type ● Registration Report ○ Poll Report ○ Survey Report

Search by time range From: 09/23/2021 To: 09/24/2021 Search

Maximum report duration: 1 Month

<input type="checkbox"/>	Scheduled Time	Topic	Meeting ID	Generate
<input type="checkbox"/>	09/24/2021 02:30:00 PM	WG5	869 5091 9755	Generate

Processing Reports:

- Download csv file and convert to Excel
- Clean Excel file as follows:
 - Sort by Name
 - Delete unique names that only participated one minute
 - Calculate the total number of participants
 - Prepare layout as per annex D
 - Convert to PDF

Annex D

